

Transformation of electric and magnetic field

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$\vec{E}$ = electric field strength in inertial system K
 $\vec{B}$ = magnetic flux density in inertial system K

$$\vec{\beta} = \frac{\vec{v}}{c} \quad \gamma = (1 - \beta^2)^{-0.5}$$

with $\vec{v}$ as velocity and c as light velocity

Relative to K the system K' moves with the constant velocity $\vec{v}$. $\vec{E}'$ and $\vec{B}'$ are the same quantities relative to system K' . With Jackson [2], equation (11.149), p.657 we have:

$$\vec{E}' = \gamma \cdot (\vec{E} + \vec{\beta} \times \vec{B}) - \frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma + 1} \cdot \vec{\beta} \cdot (\vec{\beta} \vec{E}) \quad (1)$$

$$\vec{B}' = \gamma \cdot (\vec{B} - \vec{\beta} \times \vec{E}) - \frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma + 1} \cdot \vec{\beta} \cdot (\vec{\beta} \vec{B}) \quad (2)$$

With Schröder [4], chapter 7.4, p.159, equation (113) is valid:

$$\vec{E}' = \gamma \cdot \left(\vec{E} + \frac{\vec{v}}{c} \times \vec{B} \right) - (\gamma - 1) \cdot \frac{\vec{v} \vec{E}}{v^2} \cdot \vec{v} \quad (3)$$

$$\vec{B}' = \gamma \cdot \left(\vec{B} - \frac{\vec{v}}{c} \times \vec{E} \right) - (\gamma - 1) \cdot \frac{\vec{v} \vec{B}}{v^2} \cdot \vec{v} \quad (4)$$

The equations (1) - (4) are relative to the CGS unit system of Gauss. Because of $\vec{\beta} = \frac{\vec{v}}{c}$ it is enough to show:

$$\frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma + 1} \cdot \vec{\beta} \cdot (\vec{\beta} \vec{r}) = (\gamma - 1) \cdot \frac{\vec{v} \vec{r}}{v^2} \cdot \vec{v} \quad (5)$$

$\vec{r}$ can be $\vec{E}$, $\vec{B}$ or another vector from R^3 . Equation (5) can be written in the following form:

$$\frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma + 1} \cdot \vec{\beta} \cdot (\vec{\beta} \vec{r}) = \frac{\gamma - 1}{v^2} \cdot \left(\frac{\vec{v}}{c} \cdot \vec{r} \right) \cdot \frac{\vec{v}}{c} \cdot c^2$$

With that it is sufficient to show:

$$\frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma+1} = (\gamma-1) \cdot \frac{c^2}{v^2} = \frac{\gamma-1}{\beta^2} \quad (7)$$

Now we insert:

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{a}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\beta^2}}$$

Then we obtain:

$$\frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma+1} = \frac{\frac{1}{a}}{\frac{1}{\sqrt{a}}+1} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{a}+a}$$

On the other side with $a = 1 - \beta^2$ and $\beta^2 = 1 - a$:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\gamma-1}{\beta^2} &= \frac{\frac{1}{\sqrt{a}}-1}{1-a} = \frac{1-\sqrt{a}}{\sqrt{a} \cdot (1-a)} \\ &= \frac{1-\sqrt{a}}{\sqrt{a} \cdot (1+\sqrt{a}) \cdot (1-\sqrt{a})} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{a} \cdot (1+\sqrt{a})} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{a}+a} \end{aligned}$$

With that equation (7) is shown. Also the equation (6) and (5) follows. With that the transformations of $\vec{E}$ and $\vec{B}$ in Jackson [2] and Schröder [4] are equal.

Now we change the equations (1) and (2) in the SI unit system. The quantities of CGS-system shall be denoted with a star. The quantities of SI system are without a star. Then the equations (1) and (2) can be expressed:

$$\vec{E}'^* = \gamma \cdot (\vec{E}^* + \vec{\beta} \times \vec{B}^*) - \frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma+1} \cdot \vec{\beta} \cdot (\vec{\beta} \vec{E}^*) \quad (8)$$

$$\vec{B}'^* = \gamma \cdot (\vec{B}^* - \vec{\beta} \times \vec{E}^*) - \frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma+1} \cdot \vec{\beta} \cdot (\vec{\beta} \vec{B}^*) \quad (9)$$

With Becker [1], chapter 1.3, p.13 is valid:

$$\vec{E}^* = \vec{E} \cdot \sqrt{4\pi\epsilon}$$

ϵ is the electric field constant. Besides we have with Becker [1], p.100, equation (5.1.14):

$$\vec{B}^* = c \cdot \sqrt{4\pi\epsilon} \cdot \vec{B}$$

After all insertions we get for the SI quantities:

$$\vec{E}' = \frac{1}{\sqrt{4\pi\epsilon}} \cdot \left[\gamma \cdot (\vec{E} \cdot \sqrt{4\pi\epsilon} + \vec{\beta} \times (c \cdot \sqrt{4\pi\epsilon} \cdot \vec{B})) - \frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma+1} \cdot \vec{\beta} \cdot (\vec{\beta} \cdot \vec{E} \cdot \sqrt{4\pi\epsilon}) \right]$$

$$\vec{B}' = \frac{1}{c \cdot \sqrt{4\pi\epsilon}} \cdot \left[\gamma \cdot (c\sqrt{4\pi\epsilon} \cdot \vec{B} - \vec{\beta} \times (\vec{E} \cdot \sqrt{4\pi\epsilon})) - \frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma+1} \cdot \vec{\beta} (\vec{\beta} \cdot c \cdot \sqrt{4\pi\epsilon} \cdot \vec{B}) \right]$$

Then we get the following results:

$$\vec{E}' = \gamma \cdot [\vec{E} + c \cdot (\vec{\beta} \times \vec{B})] - \frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma+1} \cdot \vec{\beta} \cdot (\vec{\beta} \vec{E}) \quad (10)$$

$$\vec{B}' = \gamma \cdot \left[\vec{B} - (\vec{\beta} \times \vec{E}) \cdot \frac{1}{c} \right] - \frac{\gamma^2}{\gamma+1} \cdot \vec{\beta} \cdot (\vec{\beta} \vec{B}) \quad (11)$$

The equations (10) and (11) are the relativistic transformations of $\vec{E}$ and $\vec{B}$ in SI unit system.

References

- [1] Becker/Sauter "Theorie der Elektrizität", volume 1, Teubner Verlag, Stuttgart, 21.edition 1973
- [2] John David Jackson "Klassische Elektrodynamik", de Gruyter Verlag, Berlin 1981
- [3] Harald Schröder "Particular problems of special relativity theory", Wissenschaft & Technik Verlag, Berlin 2002
- [4] Ulrich Schröder "Spezielle Relativitätstheorie", Verlag Harri Deutsch, 2.edition, Frankfurt on the Main 1987